

Optimization of Advanced Material Processing Techniques

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ABSTRACT:

Electro chemical discharge machining (ECDM) is a hybrid process which combines the features of electro chemical machining (ECM) and electro discharge machining (EDM). The need for micromachining of advanced engineering materials started increase in demand in various sectors like nuclear, aerospace and medical industries. Electrochemical discharge machining (ECDM) technique is that involves high-temperature melting and accelerated chemical etching under the high electrical energy discharged and has potential to machine electrically non-conductive materials such as glass, quartz, composite, ceramics. In ECDM, gas film and sparks are generated on a tool when voltage is applied between the tool and a counter electrode. Work-piece materials are removed mainly by the heat of the sparks. The spark generation is affected by both the voltage and electrolyte conditions. In this present work, The effect of process variables such as electrolyte concentration (EC), duty factor (DF), voltage (V), on response parameters such as Material Removal Rate (MRR), Tool Wear Rate (TWR),

Diametric overcut (DOC) have been investigated sodalime glass in electrochemical discharge machining (ECDM) using tungsten carbide electrode. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and F-test were performed to determine the significant parameters at a 95% confidence interval.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Nonconventional machining processes can be defined as the use of chemical, mechanical, thermal, electrical or combinations of these energies processes to machine a work-piece and remove material without contact between work-piece and tool material. Electrochemical discharge machining (ECDM) is a nontraditional machining method that has been firstly introduced for glass micro drilling by kurafuji and Suda in 1844[1]. This process is mainly used for micro-machining of hard and brittle non-conductive materials such as glass, ceramic, refractory bricks, quartz and composite materials. This has attracted extensive research interests because of additional advantage of machining electrically nonconductive materials.

The ECDM process consists of a cathode tool and an anodic work piece, which are separated by a gap filled with electrolyte (which is Depending upon the tool and work piece material, the commonly used electrolytes are NaOH, NaCl, KOH, NaNO₃, HCL, H₂SO₄, NaF etc.) and pulsed direct current (DC) power applied between them. And

connected to a D.C. power supply, consequently when a voltage higher than a critical value is applied, electrolysis in the solution starts and hydrogen bubbles grow so dense on the tool electrode (cathode) that they coalesce into a gas film. The gas film acts as an insulating layer around the tool and provides electrical potential difference between the tool and electrolyte. This leads to electrical discharges between the electrodes, thus achieving both electro chemical dissolution and electro discharge erosion of the workpiece [1]. Figure 1 shows the principle of ECDM.

Fig. 1.2 Schematic diagram of the ECDM

The electrochemical reaction for soda-lime glass workpiece ECDM is,

$$\text{SiO}_2 + 2\text{NaOH} = \text{Na}_2\text{O} - \text{SiO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$$

The sodium ion (Na⁺) and the hydroxide ion (OH⁻) in the electrolyte are adsorbed on the glass surface; the -SiO-Si-bond is broken and changed into the -Si-O-Na- bond.

Figure 2 chemical reaction of soda-lime glass workpiece

The performance of the process depends on many parameters like tool-electrode material, electrode size and shape, weld ability characteristic of tool-electrode, feedrate, work-piece material, applied voltage, current, duty cycle, pulse duration, electrolyte, its concentration and temperature, gap between tool-electrode and

workpiece, distance between cathode and anode, anode material, etc.

II. LITERATURE SARVEY:

B. Mallick, M.N. Ali, B. R. Sarkar, B. Doloi, B. [1] (2014) - They carried out experimentation and presented parametric analysis, that ECDM can be used with great potential to machine electrically non-conducting harder brittle materials such as glass and can also be employed for micro-channel cutting applications. They draw the following conclusions ECDM system. Baoyang Jiang, Shuhuai Lan, Jun Ni, Zhaoyang Zhang [2] (2014) – studied the process modeling of ECDM with respect to spark generation and material removal. Tapered tool electrodes were employed as tool electrode whereas energy distribution curve and finite element method was used to study the outputs for spark generation and material removal rate. They concluded as tapered tool improved the consistency of spark generation and suppressed the generation of minor discharge sprediction of material removal is reasonable in terms of diameter and maximum depth of machined holes.Y.S. Laio, L.C. Wu, W.Y. Peng [3] (2013) - They studied the effects of Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (SDS) surfactant added electrolyte on machining quartz in electrochemical discharge machining (ECDM). Experimental results show that, as current density is increased, there is more bubble release around the electrode. The sparks become brighter and take place in a larger area and more stable pulse current is obtained. As a result, a less taper and a better quality but a little over size hole can be drilled with a higher engraving speed. Based on the observation of sparking process together with the experimental results, a new bubble forming mechanism during ECDM when SDS added electrolyte used is inferred. Bhattacharyya and m. Malapati (2004) – in this paper, the advantages of ECDM over other machining process as absence of burr, bright surface finish and ability to machine complex shapes regardless of its hardness is expressed. They also found that, the material for tool should be chemically inert and should have good electrical conductivity. Need to use freash electrolyte everytime is essential because precipitate of electrolyte may damage the tool and will affect MRR. Flow of electrolyte has effect on machining accuracy.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP:

For this experimentation, we have selected Sodalime glass as a work piece material. Tungsten Carbide with cylindrical geometry is used as a cathode tool. All experiments has been carried out on ECDM machine. For work-piece and tool preparation we used diamond cutter and cylindrical grinder. In pre-processing the work pieces and tools were weighing on the Citizon AX 220 digital weighing machine. It is having a least count of 0.1 mg. After machining had done, again we measured weights of tools and work-pieces on same machine for calculation of material removal rate and tool wear rate values. For diametric overcut, diameter of tool is measured by Digital

Venire Caliper and diameter of hole of work-pieces is measured on Machine vision measuring system unit.

Table.4.1 Chemical Composition of soda-lime glass

Elements	SiO	Na ₂ O	Ca O	Mg O	Al ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O	SO
Weight %			10.	2.4	0.6	0.4	0.3

Table 4.2 Physical Properties of soda-lime glass

Youngs Modulus (psi)	9.8 ×106
Coeff. Of Expansion	89 × 10-7 cm/cm/ °C
Poisson Ratio	0.22
Density (mg/mm ³)	2.52 g/cm ³
Hardness (Mohs)	5.5
Strain Point	511 °C
Anneal Point	545 °C
Soften Point	724 °C

Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate also known as sodium laurel sulphate and it is a surfactant have long chain alkyl (like fatty acid, etc.) is lipophilic group.

PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES:

Melting Point – 2870 °c

Boiling Point – 6000 °c

Density -15.6 g/cm³

Thermal conductivity -28 W/m.k

Poisson Ratio- 0.2

Weight (%)- Tungsten 94%, Cobalt 6%

In electrochemical discharge machining, electrolyte is very reactive with metal. So we designed the machining chamber made of Acrylic material and bonded with chloroform which is chemically not reactive with NaOH and transparent enough to see level of electrolyte when poured in it. Special slider fixture made of SS (which is non-corrosive with NaOH electrolyte) material designed in chamber with allen bolt to fix work-piece in it. The chamber dimensions are (100 × 100 ×80) mm having 8 mm thickness. The figure shows the acrylic chamber.[5]

Fig.4.5Catia model of acrylic chamber

IV. EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS:

Following machining parameters are kept

For machining chamber the material chosen was acrylic because it is transparent in nature so that level of electrolyte can be easily detected. In addition to this it does not react with NaOH solution.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

After experimentation was carried by using Box behenken RSM methodology results of response parameters such as MRR, TWR, and DOC are noted down as follows.[7,8]

Std Order	Run Order	Pt	Volta ge	Duty Facto	Elec. Conce	MRR mg/ (min)	TWR mg/ (min)	DQC mm
						0.48	1.85	0.1728
						0.51	1.965	0.2432
						0.61	2.2	0.1322
						0.58	2.35	0.2025
						0.51	1.97	0.2257
						0.68	2.45	0.2576
						0.59	2.23	0.1457
						0.45	1.995	0.1808
						0.215	1.85	0.1767
						0.32	1.9	0.192
						0.67	2.35	0.3239
						0.395	1.675	0.2372
						0.53	2.15	0.3921
						0.515	1.955	0.2457
						0.45	2.04	0.2174

OPTIMISATION OF RESPONSE PARAMETERS BY TOPSIS METHOD:

The Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to ideal Solution (TOPSIS) is a multi-criteria decision analysis method and make ranks the alternatives according to their distances from the ideal and the negative ideal solution, i.e. the best alternative has simultaneously the shortest distance from the ideal solution and the farthest distance from the negative ideal solution. The ideal solution is identified with a hypothetical alternative that has the best values for all considered criteria whereas the negative

ideal solution is identified with a hypothetical alternative that has the worst criteria values. In practice, TOPSIS has been successfully applied to solve selection or evaluation problems with a finite number of alternatives because it is intuitive and easy to understand and implement.[6]

Following steps involved for calculating the TOPSIS values are as follows:[7]

Step 1: This step involves the development of matrix format. The row of this matrix is allocated to one alternative and each column to one attribute. The decision making matrix can be expressed as:

$$D = \begin{matrix} A_1 \\ A_2 \\ \dots \\ A_i \\ \dots \\ A_m \end{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1j} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2j} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{i1} & x_{i2} & \dots & x_{ij} & \dots & x_{in} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \dots & x_{mj} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix}$$

(i)

Here, $i A$ ($i=1, 2, \dots, m$) represents the possible alternatives; $x (j n) j=1, 2, \dots, n$ represents the attributes relating to alternative performance, $j=1, 2, \dots, n$ and $ij x$ is the performance of $i A$ with respect to attribute X_j . **Step 2:** Obtain the normalized decision matrix N_{ij} . This can be represented as:

$$N_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}}$$

(ii)

Here, N_{ij} represents the normalized performance of A_i with respect to attribute X_j

Step 3: The weighted normalized decision matrix is constructed by multiplying the normalized decision

matrix by its associated weights. The weight of each attribute was assumed to be $w_j (j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$.

$$W_{ij} = N_{ij} \times w_j$$

(iii)

Where w_j is the weight value of the j^{th} criterion, and $\sum w_j = 1$

$$\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$$

Step 4: Determine the positive-ideal solution A^+ and the negative-ideal solution A^- .

(iv)

and (v)

Where S_B and S_C denote the set of benefit criteria and set of cost criteria respectively.

Step 5: Calculate Euclidean distance.

$$s_i = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^0)^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, I.$$

(vi)

$$s_i = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^0)^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, I.$$

(vii)

Step 6: Calculate the relative closeness to the ideal solution

From Eq. (2) the decision matrix is $D_{15 \times 3}$.

$$R = \frac{s_i}{s_i + s_r}, \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, I.$$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, I.$

(viii)

Step 8: Rank the preference order.

For ranking alternatives by using this index, we can choose the best alternative with the maximum value of relative closeness.

The following procedures are used to select the best alternatives from multi-criterion TOPSIS method. **Step 1:** The objective and the important evaluation attributes are determined. For this particular problem MRR is considered as a beneficial attribute and others are considered as non-beneficial attributes (i.e.) minimization **Step 2:** All the information available is represented in the form of a DM

Table 6.2 Decision matrix for ECDM

Run Order	MRR	TWR	DOC
1	0.48	1.85	0.1728
2	0.51	1.965	0.2432
3	0.61	2.2	0.1322
4	0.58	2.35	0.2025
5	0.51	1.97	0.2257
6	0.68	2.45	0.2576
7	0.59	2.23	0.1457
8	0.45	1.995	0.1808
9	0.215	1.85	0.1767
10	0.32	1.9	0.192
11	0.67	2.35	0.3239
12	0.395	1.675	0.2372
13	0.53	2.15	0.3921
14	0.515	1.955	0.2457
15	0.45	2.04	0.2174

For that, the responses which are to be minimized Use $m_{ij} = \max x_j - x_{ij}$ $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$. Number of runs.

$j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$. Number of responses. In above input data, DOC and TWR are to be minimized so we have to use above formula for TWR, and DOC.

Max $x_i = 2.45$ for TWR and $x_i = 0.3921$

So we get, For TWR $2.45 - 1.85 = 0.6$ and for DOC $0.3921 - 0.1728 = 0.2193$. So on modified decision matrix shows as follows,

Table 6.3 Modified Decision matrix for ECDM

Run Order	MRR(mg/min)	TWR(mg/min)	DOC(mm)
	X_{ij}	X_{ij}	X_{ij}
1	0.48	0.6	0.2193

	0.51	0.485	0.1489
	0.61	0.25	0.2599
	0.58	0.1	0.1896
	0.51	0.48	0.1664
	0.68		0.1345
	0.59	0.22	0.2464
	0.45	0.455	0.2113
	0.215	0.6	0.2154
	0.32	0.55	0.2001
	0.67	0.1	0.0682
	0.395	0.775	0.1549
	0.53	0.3	
	0.515	0.495	0.1464
	0.45	0.41	0.1747
Sun	$\sum x^2_{ij}=3.97$	$\sum x^2_{ij}=2.92$	$\sum x^2_{ij}=0.49$
Square Root	1.9935	1.7116	0.7013

Step 3: The normalized matrix N_{ij} is determined by using the following formula. x

$$N_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}^2}}$$

The normalized decision matrix, $N_{18 \times 3}$, is calculated using above Eq. given as,

Table 6.4 Normalized Decision matrix for ECDM

Run	MRR(mg/min)	TWR(mg/min)	DOC(mm)
	$N_{ij} = x_{ij} / (\sum x^2_{ij})$	$N_{ij} = x_{ij} / (\sum x^2_{ij})$	$N_{ij} = x_{ij} / (\sum x^2_{ij})$
1	0.240775	0.350536	0.3126689
2	0.255824	0.28335	0.21229548
3	0.305986	0.146057	0.3705547
4	0.290937	0.058423	0.27032386
5	0.255824	0.280429	0.23724626
6	0.341099		0.19176455
7	0.295953	0.12853	0.35130696
8	0.225727	0.265823	0.30126283
9	0.107847	0.350536	0.30710844
10	0.160517	0.321324	0.28529433
11	0.336082	0.058423	0.09723675
12	0.198138	0.452775	0.22085003
13	0.265856	0.175268	

	0.258332	0.289192	0.20873108
	0.225727	0.239533	0.24908006

Above table shows the Normalized decision matrix $N_{18 \times 3}$.

Step 4: The weighted normalized decision matrix is constructed by multiplying the normalized decision matrix by its associated weights. The weight of each attribute was drawn by AHP method be $w_j(j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$.

$$W_{ij} = N_{ij} \times W_j$$

The weighted normalized value $W_{15 \times 3}$ is calculated using is given as

Table 6.5 Weighted Normalized Matrix for ECDM

Run	MRR (mg/min)			TWR (mg/min)			DOC (mm)		
	N_{ij}	W_j	W_{ij}	N_{ij}	W_j	W_{ij}	N_{ij}	W_j	W_{ij}
	0.240	0.4	0.1083	0.350	0.2	0.080	0.312	0.3	0.100
	0.255	0.4	0.1151	0.283	0.2	0.065	0.212	0.3	0.067
	0.305	0.4	0.1376	0.146	0.2	0.033	0.370	0.3	0.118
	0.290	0.4	0.1309	0.058	0.2	0.013	0.270	0.3	0.086
	0.255	0.4	0.1151	0.280	0.2	0.064	0.237	0.3	0.075
	0.341	0.4	0.1534		0.2		0.191	0.3	0.061
	0.295	0.4	0.1331	0.128	0.2	0.029	0.351	0.3	0.112
	0.225	0.4	0.1015	0.265	0.2	0.061	0.301	0.3	0.096
	0.107	0.4	0.0485	0.350	0.2	0.080	0.307	0.3	0.098
	0.160	0.4	0.0722	0.321	0.2	0.073	0.285	0.3	0.091
	0.336	0.4	0.1512	0.058	0.2	0.013	0.097	0.3	0.031
	0.198	0.4	0.0891	0.452	0.2	0.104	0.220	0.3	0.070
	0.265	0.4	0.1196	0.175	0.2	0.040		0.3	
	0.258	0.4	0.1162	0.289	0.2	0.066	0.208	0.3	0.066
	0.225	0.4	0.1015	0.239	0.2	0.055	0.249	0.3	0.079

Step 5: Determination of the positive ideal solution (A^{**}) and the negative ideal solution (A^*). These are calculated by using Eq. (4) and Eq. (5): Table 6.6 PIS and NIS values

IPS(A^{**})	0.153494	0.10413832	0.118578
NIS(A^*)	0.048531		

Step 6: The separation measure is calculated.

Table 6.7 Euclidean distance and Relative closeness to the ideal solution

Sr. No	S_i^-	S_i^+	$C^* = (S_i^- / S_i^+ + S_i^-)$
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	0.054168	0.141736	0.72349662
	0.074537	0.11531	0.60738487
	0.072293	0.152115	0.67784968
	0.098818	0.120215	0.54884449
	0.06974	0.119824	0.63210537
	0.11882	0.121585	0.50575115
	0.077539	0.143795	0.64967401
	0.070965	0.125879	0.63948812
	0.109464	0.127114	0.53730266
	0.090895	0.119826	0.56864731
	0.126021	0.108154	0.46185015
	0.08021	0.13225	0.62247234
	0.138856	0.081736	0.37053126
	0.074056	0.116066	0.61048137
	0.081314	0.110463	0.57599777

Step 7 Relative closeness of a particular alternative to the ideal solution:

It can be expressed in this step as follows.

$$C_1^* = [0.141736 / (0.054168 + 0.141736)] = 0.72349662$$

$$C_2^* = [0.11531 / (0.074537 + 0.11531)] = 0.60738487$$

And so on and given to decreasing order.

Table 6.8 Ranking of relative closeness of ECDM

Sr.No	C^*	Ranking
	0.72349662	
	0.67784968	
	0.64967401	
	0.63948812	
	0.63210537	
	0.62247234	
	0.61048137	
	0.60738487	
	0.57599777	
	0.56864731	
	0.54884449	
	0.53730266	
	0.50575115	
	0.46185015	
	0.37053126	

From the above table 6.8 it can be seen that the experimental run # 1 is the best multiple performance characteristics having highest preference order, hence it is optimum setting followed by run # 3 and # 7 for electrochemical discharge machining.

Optimum setting of parameter		
Voltage (Volt)	Electrolyte Concentration (wt %)	Duty Factor (%)

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